

Highlights

Innovation and Barriers in Industry-Academia Collaboration in Software Engineering Projects - A Tertiary Literature Review

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- Explores Industry-Academia Collaboration in software engineering projects.
- Industry-Academia Collaboration is central to SE research relevance, technology transfer, and evidence-based practice.
- Fragmented insights across many secondary studies, motivating a tertiary literature review to synthesize them into an integrative perspective.

Innovation and Barriers in Industry-Academia Collaboration in Software Engineering Projects - A Tertiary Literature Review^{*}

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ABSTRACT

Industry-academia collaboration (IAC) is a vital, yet often limited, driver of innovation in Software Engineering (SE). This study aims to strengthen collaborative project outcomes by providing an empirical overview of the effective strategies and potential risks associated with IAC. To achieve this, we conducted a tertiary systematic literature review, complemented by the snowballing technique, examining empirical evidence on secondary studies for IAC challenges and best practices reported between 2010 and 2025. Our search covered 7,236 studies and resulted in the inclusion of 30 approved secondary studies. The findings reveal a significant trend in literature reviews on IAC that has emerged since 2013, with global representation. Key results underscore that people are the most valuable resource in these collaborations. The analysis identified several collaborative models and detailed 25 categories of factors, which include 11 challenges and 14 good practices. These findings contribute to both academic knowledge and industry practices by highlighting emerging opportunities. We conclude that, while significant challenges exist, the growing global interest in IAC confirms its critical role in advancing SE innovation. We propose directions for future research.

1. Introduction

Industry–Academia Collaboration (IAC) in Software Engineering (SE) serves as a vital conduit between theoretical innovation and practical application. By fostering bidirectional knowledge exchange, IAC enables academia to ground its research in real-world complexity while enabling industry to adopt evidence-based solutions (Garousi, Petersen and Ozkan, 2016; Bamford, 2024; Barnes, Pashby and Gibbons, 2002). Collaborative projects often leverage the research strengths of academia and the practical resources and market orientation of industry, resulting in higher innovation output (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015).

Given the continuous emergence of new software technologies and development practices, IAC partnerships enable organizations and universities to update their methods, tools, and skills, thereby remaining competitive in global software markets. This dynamic is particularly impactful in software engineering, where the rapid pace of technological change demands constant adaptation and creativity to respond quickly, which is crucial to maintaining relevance and competitiveness (Lo, Nagappan and Zimmermann, 2015; Rabiser, Schmid, Becker, Botterweck, Galster, Groher and Weyns, 2018).

Although both the global software industry and SE academia increasingly pursue innovation and practical impact, empirical studies indicate that the overall level of structured collaboration remains relatively low (Garousi et al., 2016). There is a need for evidence-based strategies—such as governance mechanisms, funding models, and collaboration processes—to systematically initiate and sustain IAC projects (Garousi et al., 2016). Software engineering’s growth is shaped by different contexts and multiple influencing factors, ranging from organizational culture and management support to domain-specific requirements and collaboration mechanisms (Marijan and Gotlieb, 2021; Wohlin, Aurum, Angelis, Phillips, Dittrich, Gorschek, Grahn, Henningsson, Kagstrom, Low et al., 2011). Studies such as (Garousi,

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Pfahl, Fernandes, Felderer, Mäntylä, Shepherd, Arcuri, Coşkunçay and Tekinerdogan, 2019c) highlight substantial variation in challenges, project impacts, and proposed solutions across industrial and academic contexts in multiple countries, underscoring the complexity and contextual factors that affect growth and collaboration (Wohlin et al., 2011; Ursić, Baldacchino, Bašić, Sainz, Buljan, Hampel, Kružić, Majić, Marušić, Thetiot et al., 2022).

Skill development is another key outcome of successful collaborations (Barnes et al., 2002; Dallegrave and Santos, 2023). Industry–academia collaboration provides students and researchers with hands-on experience in solving complex real-world problems, thus bridging the gap between academic curricula and industry expectations (Marques, Dallegrave, Barbosa, Rodrigues and Santos, 2022). For industry professionals, participating in academic initiatives offers opportunities for continuous learning and exposure to emerging technologies and theories.

Well-structured collaborations can address concrete industrial problems by aligning academic research questions with pressing industry challenges, leading to context-specific solutions. Joint initiatives often target industry-specific challenges, ensuring that academic efforts yield tangible and impactful results (Figueiredo and Fernandes, 2020). Moreover, such partnerships can improve the scalability and robustness of software engineering practices by fostering an evidence-based approach to development and quality assurance (Dieste, Juristo and Martínez, 2013). Integrating academic insights and industrial expertise thus contributes to a robust ecosystem for advancing software engineering, ultimately benefiting long-term technological progress and economic growth.

Despite these recognized benefits, the path to successful collaboration is fraught with systemic challenges—ranging from misaligned timelines to cultural discrepancies between organizational and academic goals (Marijan and Gotlieb, 2021; Wohlin et al., 2011). Existing secondary studies have cataloged many of these barriers and success factors in specific IAC settings and subdomains of SE, such as particular technologies, processes, or application areas (Garousi et al., 2016, 2019c). However, a tertiary synthesis that integrates their findings into a coherent, cross-cutting perspective on IAC in SE remains lacking. As a result, the current body of knowledge is characterized by fragmented insights that do not yet provide a unified framework for practitioners and researchers to navigate the complexities of initiating, structuring, and sustaining IAC projects (Garousi et al., 2019c).

This paper reports a Tertiary Literature Review (TLR) that synthesizes existing secondary studies on IAC in SE with four main objectives: (1) to identify major research themes and directions in IAC-related secondary studies, (2) to propose a multi-dimensional framework that classifies IAC activities, strategies, and tools across collaboration phases, (3) to analyze how challenges and benefits of IAC are addressed across different SE contexts, and (4) to identify research directions that can guide future empirical and collaborative initiatives. In doing so, the study advances the state of the art by consolidating dispersed evidence into an integrative framework for IAC in SE and by outlining a structured research agenda for both researchers and practitioners.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides the theoretical background and reviews related studies. Section 3 outlines the methodology employed in this review. Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 discusses observations, lessons learned, and recommendations, while Section 6 addresses threats to validity. Finally, Section 7 offers concluding thoughts and suggestions for future work.

2. Background

Some studies indicate that cooperation is essential in advancing software engineering and fosters innovation (Philbin, 2008; Petersen, Gencel, Asghari, Baca and Betz, 2014; Sandberg, Pareto and Arts, 2011). However, the main challenge is aligning the objectives and needs of both industry and academia. While the industry focuses on product development, academia prioritizes the generation of new knowledge. Academic research requires rigorous methodologies to enable other researchers to accurately replicate the steps involved. This approach ensures a clearer understanding of the context relevant to specific investigations (Wohlin, Aurum, Angelis, Phillips, Dittrich, Gorschek, Grahn, Henningson, Kagstrom, Low, Rovegard, Tomaszewski, van Toorn and Winter, 2012). This section covers relevant works to deepen the discussion of the research.

Evans et al. research (Evans, Miklosik and Du, 2023) examines various partnerships between academic institutions and industries, emphasizing their role in facilitating digital transformation. The study identifies several types of collaborations, including joint research initiatives, shared use of facilities and equipment, innovation and commercialization efforts, student-led projects, and collaborative teaching and learning programs. The benefits of these partnerships encompass access to valuable resources, validation of work, learning and teaching opportunities, financial benefits, an enhanced reputation, and career advancement. The authors also discuss enablers that facilitate successful collaborations, such as effective communication, mutual trust, aligned objectives, and supportive organizational structures.

Table 1
Related Works

Work	Goal
Evans (2023)	Explores different types of collaborations, highlighting their impact on driving digital transformation.
Marques (2022)	How industry and academia collaborate specifically in the context of Agile methodologies
Marijan (2022)	Identify effective and ineffective practices in industry-academia collaborations, providing patterns and anti-patterns based on 14 years of experience to improve knowledge co-creation and research impact in software engineering.
Dallegrave (2021)	Analyzes the alignment of skills and competencies, highlighting a significant gap from practitioners' perspectives that calls for updating academic curricula to better meet industry demands.
Cico (2021)	investigates the alignment between industry trends and educational practices in software engineering
Garousi (2019)	Assessed the knowledge gaps of software engineers by comparing the knowledge learned in universities with the skills needed in the software industry.
Cico (2019)	A comprehensive overview of how SE education can better align with industry trends
Garousi (2016)	Analyze studies related to industry-academia collaborations in SE
Petersen (2014)	How action research can serve as an effective framework for fostering IAC.
Wohlin (2012)	Examines critical factors that contribute to effective partnerships between academic institutions and industry organizations, with a focus on SE
Lamprecht (2012)	Frameworks and approaches for fostering effective collaboration between universities and the software industry in South Africa.
Sandberg (2011)	How principles from agile methodologies can be applied to enhance collaboration between industry and academia

The article highlights the significance of these collaborative efforts in driving digital innovation and transformation across various sectors. Their research highlights the need for a more empirical and nuanced understanding of how these partnerships operate, the types of collaboration that are most effective, and the enablers and barriers in real-world contexts that foster beneficial digital transformation outcomes. This research also underscores the importance of a more in-depth examination of the practical interactions and synergies that drive digital transformation through university-industry partnerships. To identify additional enablers and barriers in real-world settings that affect the success and sustainability of these collaborations. The present study aims to address this gap and to contribute to the empirical evidence on industry-academia collaboration in software engineering.

Marques et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive literature review on IAC and software agility, using a systematic literature review (SLR) and snowball sampling across five databases. This study analyzed 8,460 articles. As a result, 10 categories were identified that describe the challenges faced in this field, along with 14 categories that describe relevant effective practices. Additionally, this research provided a detailed examination of seven collaboration models. This study focused specifically on the context of agile software development. The current research proposal aims to extend this scope to encompass the broader domain of software engineering.

Marijan and Sen (2022) examines the challenges inherent in industry-academia research collaborations in software engineering, identifying the “*problem of two cultures*,” the disconnection between academic research and practical realities, and misaligned temporal expectations as significant barriers to effective knowledge transfer and collaborative success. They propose a set of patterns and anti-patterns derived from extensive qualitative data to facilitate improved knowledge co-creation between academic researchers and industry practitioners, thus bridging the research-practice divide (Marijan and Sen, 2022). This work is closely related to the present study and additionally emphasizes enhancing collaboration through the application of pattern-based design and deeper empirical investigation. Within this research, our objective is to further examine and refine these identified patterns and anti-patterns to facilitate more effective knowledge co-creation.

Dallegrave, Vasconcelos, Alves and Santos (2021) investigated the alignment between academia and the software industry, focusing on skill development within agile software development practices. Through an exploratory and quantitative survey involving 161 participants, including students, professionals, and professors from multiple countries, the study found a significant perception gap: academics generally believed their skills and curricula were moderately

aligned with industry needs, while practitioners considered this alignment unsatisfactory. The results highlight the low level of collaboration between academia and industry in agile contexts, pointing out challenges such as poorly defined collaboration problems and the fast-changing, iterative nature of agile projects. This misalignment underscores the need for improved industry-academia collaboration and curriculum updates to better prepare students for real-world agile development environments and close the existing knowledge gap between research and practice (Dallegrave et al., 2021). This study primarily highlights the gap in Computer Science curricula, which have not evolved adequately to keep pace with rapid advancements in industry-agile practices, leaving graduates inadequately prepared for real-world agile environments. While the study acknowledges the gap between academia and industry in collaborative projects, its main emphasis is on academic curriculum development. In contrast, our research seeks to actively promote and enhance collaboration by focusing on the collaborative projects themselves, leveraging identified patterns and anti-patterns among partners to facilitate more effective cooperation.

The study by Garousi, Borg and Oivo (2020) reflects the practical relevance of software engineering research. In addition to a significant effort to reestablish IAC initiatives, their study quotes: *"many researchers and practitioners believe that we, as a community, are still struggling with the relevance and utility of research."* Their research compiles the evidence of opinions shared on this topic in the SE community. This study conducted a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) of 54 systematically selected sources (non-peer-reviewed papers and articles). Their results include (1) researchers who have wrong views on SE in practice, (2) the need for connection with industry, and (3) the wrong identification of research problems. To resolve that, their suggestions are: (1) Using appropriate research approaches, such as action research; (2) Choosing relevant (practical) research problems; and (3) Collaborating with industry. The study emphasizes the importance of continual synthesis and critical reflection on community experiences to deepen understanding and facilitate shifts in priorities that enhance the practical relevance of software engineering research.

A published study by Cico and Jaccheri (2019) conducted a systematic mapping study to analyze and categorize the literature on software engineering trends relevant to academia and industry. The study concludes that there is a substantial gap between current SE education and industry needs, mainly due to rapid technological advances and changing industry practices. For SE education to remain relevant, it must evolve to reflect these trends. Aligning educational programs with industry demands can help ensure that graduates enter the workforce with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in modern software engineering roles (Cico, Jaccheri, Nguyen-Duc and Zhang, 2021). This study highlights the disconnect between software engineering education and the rapidly evolving demands of the software industry, underscoring the need for curriculum reform and strengthened collaboration between academia and industry to effectively address this gap.

Garousi, Giray and Tuzun (2019a) provides an empirical analysis based on the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK) and survey data from 129 practitioners to map knowledge gaps between university education and industry needs in software engineering. Their findings recommend enhancements in curricula to better align academic knowledge with practical skills required by the software industry, addressing a crucial knowledge gap in collaborative settings (Garousi et al., 2019a).

Garousi et al. (2016) conducted a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) highlighting the benefits of collaboration between academia and industry, providing insights into industry needs, proposed solutions, and the impact of these initiatives. This research identified 64 challenges, 128 patterns, and 36 anti-patterns in the application of IAC in Software Engineering. In addition, various other studies explore challenges and success patterns in IAC projects (Sandberg et al., 2011; Lamprecht and van Rooyen, 2012; Wohlin et al., 2012; Petersen et al., 2014; Garousi et al., 2019c; Garousi, Giray, Tuzun, Catal and Felderer, 2019b). Recently SLR conducted by Marques et al. (Marques, Dallegrave, de Oliveira and Santos, 2023) analyzed 8,640 articles and approved 21 primary studies. It reported 76 good practices, 37 challenges, and 7 collaboration models.

This study provides empirical evidence to the growing body of knowledge on industry-academia collaboration (IAC). Building upon the investigations of Marques et al. (2023), our research expands the scope by incorporating secondary studies and addressing a broader contextual landscape. To achieve this, we employ a systematic tertiary literature review to synthesize empirical findings into a cohesive framework.

Furthermore, we address current research fragmentation by introducing a multidimensional taxonomy of IAC initiatives. This paper contributes a novel classification of collaboration models, mapping specific tools and strategies to partnership maturity levels. Finally, we offer a set of evidence-based recommendations, transforming theoretical challenges into a structured decision-making guide for Software Engineering (SE) stakeholders.

Figure 1: Research Process (Based on Garousi et al. 2016).

3. Materials and Methods

This research follows the systematic review protocol established by Keele et al. (Keele et al., 2007), Brereton et al. (Brereton, Kitchenham, Budgen, Turner and Khalil, 2007), Petersen et al. (Petersen, Vakkalanka and Kuzniarz, 2015), Kitchenham et al. (Kitchenham, 2004), and Hennessy et al. (Hennessy, Johnson and Keenan, 2019). A systematic literature review provides a means to evaluate and interpret available research relevant to a specific area of interest. According to Keele et al. (Keele et al., 2007), a systematic review consists of three phases: planning, conducting, and reporting. Each research phase follows a systematic approach and adheres to established guidelines. The progression to the next phase requires thorough completion, review, and validation of the current stage to ensure rigor, coherence, and credibility. These phases can be observed in Figure 1. In addition, we follow the guidelines outlined in (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017; Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, Pandey and Lim, 2021) for the bibliometric and mapping analyses. This research focuses on secondary studies that address the challenges and best practices of industry-academia collaboration across various software engineering project contexts.

The development of the systematic literature review protocol was mainly inspired by the review of Garousi et al. (2016). Other literature reviews were identified during the research protocol review process, such as those of Cico and Jaccheri (2019) and Marques et al. (2022), which focus exclusively on primary articles. This recognition revealed a gap in the analysis of secondary and tertiary studies, highlighting the need for a more comprehensive approach to these sources in the existing literature.

A tertiary review synthesizes multiple existing systematic reviews—secondary studies—to provide a comprehensive understanding of industry-academia collaboration at a higher level. Since current secondary studies often focus narrowly on specific contexts, methodologies, or regions, a tertiary review helps integrate these fragmented insights into a holistic perspective. This comprehensive approach enables the identification of overarching trends, research gaps, and unresolved challenges that individual reviews may overlook. It also supports the development of more evidence-based models and practical strategies by consolidating validated knowledge from prior works. Additionally, we aim to extend the empirical validation and to examine the factors influencing collaboration success. Ultimately, this strategy optimizes research efforts by reducing redundancy and advancing both theoretical understanding and practical applications in software engineering collaboration (Kitchenham, Pretorius, Budgen, Brereton, Turner, Niazi and Linkman, 2010; Keele et al., 2007; Marijan and Gotlieb, 2021).

3.1. Planning

The goal is to systematically collect, evaluate, and interpret all published studies relevant to specific research questions, providing consolidated information, highlighting the benefits of different approaches, and identifying gaps that require further investigation (Keele et al., 2007). To comprehend the current research landscape regarding Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) in Software Engineering (SE), the following questions have been formulated:

Table 2
Selected Review Sources

Publisher	URL
IEEE Xplore	ieeexplore.ieee.org
ACM Digital Library	portal.acm.org
Springer Link	link.springer.com
Scopus	www.scopus.com
Science Direct	www.sciencedirect.com

Main question: "What do secondary studies evidence the current state of research on industry-academia collaborations in SE?"

3.1.1. Research Questions

RQ1: What secondary studies (SLRs) have been published on Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) in Software Engineering (SE)? This question maps the bibliometric landscape of SLRs, capturing publication trends including timelines, venues, key researchers, and institutions conducting IAC research in SE.

RQ2: What research topics do these SLRs investigate? This question synthesizes the thematic content across identified SLRs, highlighting the most frequently investigated topics and research focus within IAC in SE.

RQ3: What gaps and future research directions emerge from these SLRs? This question extracts high-level research gaps, unanswered questions, and proposed future directions identified within the SLRs on IAC in SE.

RQ4: What types and models of IAC exist in SE? This question classifies and defines distinct IAC models and types reported in the SLRs, including their defining characteristics and applicable contexts in SE.

RQ5: What specific activities, strategies, and practices support IAC implementation in SE? This question compiles concrete activities, strategies, guidelines, and best practices proposed across SLRs to facilitate successful IAC execution, addressing implementation challenges and solutions. The objective is to collect guidelines that help researchers and professionals in creating strategies for managing collaborations.

3.1.2. Sources

Based on the guidelines of Petersen et al. (2015) and Keele et al. (2007), search engines for academic articles were selected as a strategy to search for data and articles for research. The search process considered journals, conferences, and workshops indexed in five renowned, specialized digital libraries in computer science and related fields, as presented in Table 2. These are recommended sources of articles for software engineering researchers, as they provide access to important journals and conferences in the field.

3.1.3. Search String

Keywords and synonyms related to the investigation were combined to form a relevant search string to select articles strongly related to the topic (Petersen et al., 2015; Kitchenham, Brereton, Budgen, Turner, Bailey and Linkman, 2009; Perkmann and Walsh, 2009). It was defined as follows: This research is based on Garousi et al. (2016), who conducted an RSL between 1995 and 2014 using ACM, IEEE, and Google Scholar as automatic search engines. For the present study, we include specific contexts in software engineering. We observed some limitations in the structure of the string cited in Garousi et al. (2016). Consequently, we opted to implement additional changes to replace the terms 'practice', 'theory', 'software', 'IT' and 'education'. This adjustment aims to enhance the representation, alignment, and synonyms of these concepts.

Table 3
Search String

Automatic Search
("Industry-Academia Collaboration" OR "Industry Education Intersection" OR "Collaborative Practice Research") AND ("Systematic literature review" OR "Systematic mapping study" OR "Systematic literature mapping" OR "Review of studies")
Based on Garousi et al. (2016) and Marques et al. (2022)

Table 4
Quasi-Gold Articles

ID	Title
A238	Challenges and best practices in industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review
A164	Industry-Academy Collaboration in Agile Methodology: a Systematic Literature Review
A078	Practical relevance of software engineering research: synthesizing the community's voice
<i>Based on Zhang and Babar (2010)</i>	

Table 5
Revised Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

ID	Inclusion Criteria (IC)	ID	Exclusion Criteria (EC)
IC1	Secondary studies (SLRs or Mapping Studies) specifically addressing Collaborative Research for Industry-Academia Collaboration.	EC1	Primary studies, case studies, or surveys without a systematic review methodology.
IC2	Peer-reviewed articles published in journals or conference proceedings.	EC2	Grey literature, editorials, tutorials, posters, or short papers (< 4 pages).
IC3	Studies published between 2010 and 2025.	EC3	Full-text not available electronically or not written in English.
IC4	Studies meeting the minimum Quality Assessment (QA) threshold (Score \geq 5.0).	EC4	Duplicate studies (only the most recent or complete version is retained).

3.1.4. *Quasi-gold Standard (QGS)*

According to Zhang and Babar (2010), a list of *Quasi-Gold Standard (QGS)* should be established in the search results to validate the performance of the strings. Articles from QGS not included in search results should be reviewed to determine the reasons for their exclusion. A new search string should incorporate these articles in the following search. This process should continue until all relevant articles are identified in the automatic search results.

3.1.5. *Selection Criteria*

Inclusion (I) and Exclusion (E) criteria were defined to assist in the study selection process. The requirements are in Table 5. To be accepted for this review, all selection criteria must be met.

3.1.6. *Quality Assessment*

To ensure the methodological rigor of this tertiary study, the quality of the included secondary studies was evaluated through a structured, independent review. The Quality Criteria (QC) for the studies were evaluated based on the guidelines proposed by Dyba, Dingsoyr and Hanssen (2007), which are outlined in the following quality guidelines:

Reporting: The clarity of the study objectives and the context in which it is conducted;

Credibility: The rigor of the research methods used to validate data collection tools and analysis;

Rigor: It assesses the credibility of research methods to ensure that they are valid and meaningful;

Table 6
Quality Assessment

QC1	Are the inclusion and exclusion criteria well-defined and adequate?	Rigor
QC2	Does the search cover all relevant primary studies?	Credibility
QC3	Were the included studies synthesized?	Reporting
QC4	Does the secondary study assess the quality of the studies included?	Relevance
QC5	Did the secondary study provide data on the primary studies?	Reporting

Based on (Dyba et al., 2007)

Relevance: Discuss the significance of the study for both the software industry and the research community.

The qualitative attributes of each study were quantified using a three-point Likert scale, following the recommendations of (Lima, Júnior, Moya, Almeida, Anjos, Lencastre, Fagundes and Alencar, 2019). Each criterion (see Table 6) was assigned a numerical value as follows: Yes (Y): 1.0 (the study fully satisfies the criterion); Partially (P): 0.5 (the criterion is addressed but lacks sufficient detail or clarity); No (N): 0.0 (the study fails to meet the criterion or the information is absent). The assessment was conducted by two independent reviewers. In cases of persistent disagreement regarding the scoring or classification of a specific study, a senior supervisor acted as an arbitrator to resolve the conflict and determine the final consensus score. This tripartite structure was implemented to minimize subjective bias and ensure the reproducibility of the evaluation.

Upon consolidation of the scores, studies were categorized based on their cumulative performance relative to the maximum possible quality score. Only studies achieving a final quality score exceeding 50% of the total possible points were retained for data synthesis. Studies with a classification equal to or lower than 50% were excluded from further analysis, as they were deemed to possess insufficient methodological robustness or inadequate reporting quality.

To measure the reliability of the review process and the degree of agreement between the two primary reviewers, Cohen (1968) coefficient was calculated. This statistical measure accounts for the magnitude of agreement occurring by chance. The resulting coefficients were interpreted according to the Landis and Koch scale, with values above 0.61 indicating substantial agreement.

3.2. Conducting

This systematic review followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page, McKenzie, Bossuyt, Boutron, Hoffmann, Mulrow, Shamseer, Tetzlaff, Akl, Brennan et al., 2021). Automatic searches were last updated in February 2026 in the following databases: ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, and ScienceDirect. Additionally, a manual search was done, and forward and backward snowballing were applied in two rounds.

The automated search process used a specific search string across multiple digital repositories to locate studies. Initially, this process identified 724 secondary studies. However, after applying the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria, 89 studies were chosen. A more detailed examination of their titles, abstracts, and keywords reduced this number to 38. In the quality assessment stage, the full texts of the selected studies were reviewed to ensure they met quality requirements and effectively addressed the research questions, ultimately leading to the selection of six studies in Table 7.

The snowballing technique was used to comprehensively include relevant studies and strengthen the evidence (Wohlin, 2014). Initially, this method reviewed 1,454 citations drawn from the six selected secondary studies and 5,058 in the second (6,512 total). Following a thorough evaluation, 3429 studies were identified for further detailed analysis. Through an in-depth review and quality assessment, 15 studies were eventually selected in the first round. After completing the first screening round, which approved 21 articles, a second round was conducted to further strengthen the robustness of our evidence. This process included 30 studies in the final review, as shown in Figure 2.

3.3. Quality Control

This phase systematically assesses the methodological rigor of the secondary studies analyzed. It employs a set of quality criteria (QC01–QC05) to evaluate each study, focusing on inclusion/exclusion criteria, search coverage, synthesis, quality assessment, and data reporting (see Table 6).

Figure 2: Tertiary Review Stages.

Table 7

Automatic Search Results

ID	Title	Authors
A238	Challenges and best practices in industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review	Garousi (2016)
A217	Leveraging organizational climate theory for understanding industry-academia collaboration	Sherman (2018)
A081	What makes industry-university collaboration succeed? A systematic review of the literature	Rybnicek (2019)
A078	Practical relevance of software engineering research: synthesizing the community voice	Garousi (2020)
A232	Exploring the intersection between software industry and Software Engineering Education - A systematic mapping of Software Engineering Trends	Cico (2021)
A164	Industry-Academy Collaboration in Agile Methodology: a Systematic Literature Review	Marques (2022)

The quality assessment revealed that although high-quality systematic literature reviews (SLRs) are relatively uncommon within the examined body of research, exemplary studies such as Garousi et al. (2016) (Garousi et al., 2016), Rybnicek and Königgruber (2019) (Rybnicek and Königgruber, 2019), and Garousi et al. (2020) (Garousi et al., 2020) demonstrate that rigorous methodological standards and comprehensive reporting are achievable within this domain. These studies satisfy all five quality criteria, reflecting methodological robustness, transparent synthesis, and methodological transparency. However, the majority of reviewed SLRs only partially meet these standards, often exhibiting methodological limitations, such as a restricted search scope—consulting only a limited number of databases or journals—thereby increasing the risk of omitting relevant evidence. Additionally, many reviews fail to conduct or clearly describe explicit quality assessments of the included primary studies, thereby diminishing the reliability and validity of their conclusions. Other recurring weaknesses include insufficient detail in reporting primary study characteristics and vague descriptions of synthesis procedures. Conversely, the small subset of high-quality SLRs displays notable methodological strengths: they apply clearly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria, conduct comprehensive and systematic searches across multiple databases, and provide transparent accounts of their synthesis

Table 8
Data Extraction Information

Information	Questions
Bibliometrics: <i>title, author, year and place of publication, etc.</i>	RQ1
Research facet: <i>goals, topics addressed and gaps</i>	RQ2
Contribution facet: <i>practical knowledge</i>	RQ3
Contribution facet: <i>IAC types and models</i>	RQ4
Contribution facet: <i>IAC anti-patterns and patterns</i>	RQ5

methods and quality appraisal processes. These studies also offer detailed data on the reviewed primary studies, thereby enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and overall confidence in their findings.

3.4. Data Synthesis and Thematic Mapping

We began coding and categorizing the data based on the primary studies identified through the systematic literature review (SLR) and the snowballing method (detailed in Appendix A: Selected Studies). The data extraction procedure was carried out in multiple iterative stages. The data characteristics were identified and collected from every publication for each research question. When uncertainties arose, the second author conducted a cross-validation of the data.

For the analysis of the results, we utilized electronic spreadsheets, while Atlas TI software¹ was employed to create simplified results, code, and categorize the data. This tool was developed by Muhr (1991), based on *grounded theory*. Analysis and coding were conducted according to the principles outlined by Charmaz (2006), where both open and axial coding were employed to develop subcategories and categories during data analysis. This approach allowed for a rigorous transformation of raw evidence into a structured thematic framework.

Open Coding and Parameter Analysis: Initial data extraction involved the creation of primary codes directly from the study findings. To ensure the relevance of these codes, we utilized two key metrics within the software:

- *Groundedness:* This parameter measured the frequency of specific observations across the literature, identifying the most "saturated" concepts.
- *Density:* This indicated the level of interconnectedness between codes, helping to reveal complex relationships and dependencies between research variables.

Categorical Grouping: Following the initial coding phase, codes were synthesized into categorical groups. This iterative refinement process moved the analysis from individual data points to higher-order themes. This structural mapping was essential for identifying common trends and methodological gaps in the existing literature.

Thematic Discovery: The final synthesis resulted in a comprehensive overview of the field, where the interplay between groundedness and density served as the objective basis for identifying the most significant "pillars" of current research. This systematic approach ensures that the final conclusions are not merely anecdotal but are derived from a verifiable and reproducible analytical process.

3.5. Verifiability and Replicability

To facilitate replication and further exploration of our study by other researchers, we have prepared a replication package² containing the complete set of results obtained during this investigation.

- Research Protocol
 - Search string for each database automatic search;
 - Results selection from each phase of the research;
 - Quality assessment results;
 - Codes (thematic discovery);

¹<https://atlasti.com/>

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15039279>

Figure 3: SRL publications evolution.

- Data extraction;
- References;
- PRISMA 2020 Checklists

4. Results

Collaboration is a complex and multifaceted process influenced by individual qualities, organizational practices, and broader institutional frameworks. Understanding this complexity requires examining how personal traits, such as expertise and motivation, interact with environmental factors, including organizational culture and institutional regulations (Perkmann, Tartari, McKelvey, Autio, Broström, D’este, Fini, Geuna, Grimaldi, Hughes et al., 2013). To enhance our understanding of this process, we present a summary of the study’s findings below, highlighting the key factors at each level.

4.1. RQ1: What secondary studies (SLRs) have been published on Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) in Software Engineering (SE)?

As indicated in Figure 2, the automatic search resulted in 724 articles, to which an additional 6,512 articles were added through the Snowballing process, totaling 7236 articles, with 30 articles selected in the final phase. This underscores the contemporary relevance of Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) and reveals a critical gap in research that addresses its current dynamics and modern challenges in Software Engineering.

Pereira et al. (Pereira and Franco, 2022) found in their review that the topic of cooperation between universities and small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) has been evolving since the first studies emerged in 1995, with significant growth after 2014. This research focuses on knowledge transfer, which is at the heart of most collaborative efforts. However, SMEs face challenges accessing university programs that could support their growth, primarily due to a lack of awareness of available programs and how to navigate them.

This research could not identify any other tertiary studies that have systematically synthesized and summarized the studies mentioned above. Our findings indicate a consistent trend since 2013, except for 2014, 2016, and 2023, in which at least one systematic review study has been published annually on the topic of industry-academia collaboration, as shown in Figure 3. This demonstrates the academic community’s commitment to consistently highlighting and addressing this critical issue.

Figure 4: Researchers' geographic distribution.

The distribution of publications among the mentioned countries indicates a diverse and extensive global representation. Figure 4 represents the frequency and location distribution of researchers who have published systematic reviews in recent years. This distribution highlights the potential for valuable partnerships and provides insight into the collaboration landscape between industry and academia. European countries dominate the list, with a strong focus on collaboration within the European Union and its neighboring regions. The United Kingdom and Sweden lead with a frequency of 6, showing their significant contributions to the topic. Portugal and Brazil participated well, with 5 and 4 articles, respectively. Spain and Germany follow with frequencies of 3, reflecting moderate involvement. Austria, France, the USA, Canada, Norway, and China have a frequency of 2, indicating occasional contributions. Additionally, Latin American countries, such as Brazil and Peru, have established regional partnerships and collaborations with North America. Countries such as Finland, Israel, Turkey, Italy, Denmark, Ecuador, and others appear with a frequency of 1, suggesting minimal engagement in our analysis. Overall, this visualization highlights the global nature of contributions, with European countries prominently represented alongside contributors from North America, Asia, and South America.

4.2. RQ2: What research topics do these SLRs investigate?

This research question categorizes and visualizes key topics in selected articles that focus on industry-academia collaboration (IAC). These articles encompass systematic reviews of the literature, theoretical explorations, and empirical studies on the dynamics, challenges, and outcomes of collaborations. The topics listed below will be discussed in more detail:

- Collaboration Dynamics (challenges and success factors):** Includes barriers, facilitators, and best practices. The topic is discussed in articles such as [A232] (Cico et al., 2021), [A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019), [A217], (Sherman, Hadar and Luria, 2018), [E116] (PESTI, TAMÁŠOVÁ, LAJČIN and BODONYI, 2021), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016);
- Practical relevance and knowledge transfer:** Focus on long-term knowledge sharing and integration, models, processes, and ecosystem design to transfer innovations from academia to industry ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [A232] (Cico et al., 2021), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [C1125] (Faisal, Chong and Yee, 2017));

- **Educational Integration:** Maps trends in software engineering education and how these align with industry demands, stressing the importance of agile methodologies and practical training ([A232] (Cico et al., 2021), [A164] (Marques et al., 2022));
- **Innovation and Organizational Culture:** Uses organizational climate theory to understand how culture impacts innovation in collaborations ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018), [A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019));
- **Stakeholder Engagement (determinants, challenges, and mutual benefits):** Explores how academic and industry stakeholders derive value from collaboration through shared goals and mutual trust to overcome collaboration barriers ([E092] (Figueiredo and Fernandes, 2020), [E463] (Singh and Kaundal, 2022), [E465] (Zhuang and Shi, 2024), [A164] (Marques et al., 2022), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015));
- **Technology Transfer:** Examines the practical relevance of software engineering research, emphasizing the need for actionable knowledge transfer to industry stakeholders ([C1125] (Faisal et al., 2017), [B077] (Brings, Daun, Brinckmann, Keller and Weyer, 2018), [E062] (Maresova, Stemberkova and Fadeyi, 2019), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015), [B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013), [C1322] (Arenas and González, 2018), [C1352] (Good, Knockaert, Soppe and Wright, 2019));
- **Software Engineering and Digital Innovation:** Discusses innovation as a key outcome of successful collaborations, emphasizing mutual benefits ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [A232] (Cico et al., 2021), [E144] (Ford, Portz, Zhou, Gornail, Moore, Zhang and Bull, 2021));
- **Public Support and Open Innovation:** explores the role of public support and open innovation in fostering collaborations ([C1047] (Jugend, Fiorini, Armellini and Ferrari, 2020));
- **Industry-Specific Applications:** examines digital health collaborations, identifying benefits, facilitators, and recommendations for partnerships in the health-tech sector. Also, it emphasizes local challenges and enablers ([E144] (Ford et al., 2021), [E147] (Jugend et al., 2020));
- **Methodological Approaches:** Focuses on empirical studies in the software industry, discussing how collaborations are designed and evaluated through systematic experiments ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [A164] (Marques et al., 2022));
- **Academic and Industry Roles:** Highlights the dual role in balancing commercialization goals with knowledge dissemination. ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015), [B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013));
- **Regional Development and Economic Impact:** Offers a context-sensitive perspective, identifying how local and national factors influence collaboration outcomes ([E066] (Pereira and Franco, 2023), [E084] (Pereira and Franco, 2022), [E375] (Nsanzumuhire and Groot, 2020));

Cico et al. (Cico et al., 2021) highlight that trending topics in software engineering (SE) research include agile software development, software implementation, usability and value, global software engineering, lean software start-up, and systems of systems.

Our analysis indicates that the frequent appearance of topics such as *Collaboration Dynamics* and *Software Engineering and Digital Innovation* suggests that researchers prioritize understanding the operational aspects and technological impacts of collaborations. Furthermore, the moderate focus on topics such as *Stakeholder Engagement* and *Technology Transfer* underscores the importance of practical frameworks for improving collaboration effectiveness. The lower frequency of *Public Support*, *Organizational Culture*, and *Open Innovation* and *Academic and Industry Roles* suggests areas for further research that could yield valuable insights. This can be summarized in Figure 5.

4.3. RQ3: What gaps and future research directions emerge from these SLRs?

This question examines the empirical knowledge presented in the analyzed articles, providing essential and general insights into collaborations. The key findings highlight the importance of recognizing people as the most valuable resource in collaborative research. It emphasizes the need for strong relationships within the research community and warns against making incorrect assumptions and oversimplifying research problems (Garousi et al., 2020; Marques et al., 2022).

Figure 5: Frequency of topics.

A vital recommendation includes addressing potential disconnect and lack of experience, organizing regular workshops with industry partners, fostering continuous learning, ensuring active management engagement, appointing a dedicated project champion, establishing research in real-world problems, explicitly demonstrating benefits to industry partners, adopting an agile approach during collaboration, and assigning researchers to work closely with industry partners (Garousi et al., 2016).

In addition, our observations indicate a significant change in the approach of a collaborative partner following the study conducted by (Garousi et al., 2016). Previously, their focus was primarily on preparing students for the industry. However, it is now evident that they are actively implementing the identified patterns. This shift represents a strategic transition from simply understanding theory to applying these practice patterns to enhance the effectiveness of collaborative initiatives. Reflects a more substantial commitment to translating theoretical insights into practical strategies for smoother integration between academia and industry.

There is limited focus on the impact of organizational culture on collaboration success. Expanding this focus could enhance integration strategies. In addition, research on the role of government and public policies could inform funding and resource allocation for collaborative efforts. Another identified research gap is the need for insight into sector-specific challenges, such as those in healthcare and manufacturing, to tailor collaboration models.

These articles collectively emphasize the complexity and interconnectedness of IAC processes. The key factors influencing the success of these partnerships include public policies, institutional frameworks, and sustainable collaboration practices. The insights gained from this analysis are valuable to policymakers, academic institutions, and industry leaders seeking to improve collaboration effectiveness and innovation outcomes.

4.4. RQ4: What types and models of IAC exist in SE?

This question assesses the various types of Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) discussed in the literature. These models emphasize the mechanisms, outcomes, and contextual factors that lead to successful collaborations. Below is a summary of the main themes and insights derived from the literature.

4.4.1. Collaboration Types

Perkmann et al. (Perkmann and Walsh, 2009) classify university-industry research collaboration projects between universities and industries into four types, distinguished by their proximity to the market: problem-solving, technology development, idea testing, and knowledge generation. Singh's study (Singh and Kaundal, 2022) highlights various interactions between academia and industry, including cooperative research, technology transfer, joint ventures, and consulting. It also discusses various channels for collaboration, including publications, patents, joint research projects, and internships, while distinguishing between informal and formal connections (Singh and Kaundal, 2022).

- **Research-oriented collaborations:** Creating knowledge through collaborative research initiatives. Studies emphasize the importance of aligning practical industry needs with academic research objectives ([A238])

(Garousi et al., 2016), [B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)). In addition, [A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019) emphasizes the importance of collaborative governance for long-term engagement. Universities often provide expert consulting services to the industry or conduct contract research in which the results are expected to solve specific problems for the company [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015).

- **Technology transfer and innovation:** Transfer of academic research to commercialized technologies [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015), [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019). This collaboration involves commercializing university research through patents, licensing agreements, and the creation of spin-off companies [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015). [B077] (Brings et al., 2018) and [C1322] (Arenas and González, 2018) discuss technology transfer models, emphasizing structured knowledge-transfer processes. [C1047] (Jugend et al., 2020) links public support mechanisms with effective innovation results.
- **Education-centric collaborations:** Enhance student training through industry internships, projects, and joint curriculum development. [A232] (Cico et al., 2021) Identify emerging trends in software engineering integrated into academic curricula. [E092] (Figueiredo and Fernandes, 2020) and [E084] (Pereira and Franco, 2022) advocate for SME-specific partnerships to promote regional development. Industry partnerships also offer students opportunities to work on real-world projects through internships, co-op programs, or collaborative degree programs. This helps students gain practical experience and industry knowledge [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015).

4.4.2. Collaboration Models

Identified forms of Innovation and Collaboration (IAC) include the following: continuing education programs, patenting, technology transfer offices, science parks or incubators, cross-sector collaborations, public-private partnerships (PPPs), technology transfer models, cooperative method development (CMD), softCoDer, dialogical action research (DAR), collaborative practice research (CPR), the ARN model, the Certus model, reflective systems development (RSD), a spiral model for innovation-based industrial development, and an architectural model for IACs [A164] (Marques et al., 2022). Models can be categorized into the following groups:

- **Linear Model:** Describes the process of transfer of academic research to commercial technologies [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015). This model assumes a one-way flow of knowledge that begins with basic research conducted at universities. Then, it progresses through applied research and development, ultimately leading to commercialization in the industry. In this framework, universities generate new knowledge passed on to industry [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019).
- **Interactive or network models:** More recent models understand technology transfer as an interactive and dynamic process. These models emphasize the importance of collaboration among universities, industry, and other stakeholders, involving multiple feedback loops. Universities and industries collaborate through partnerships and networks to develop, adapt, and commercialize technology [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019).
- **Triple helix model:** The model emphasizes the importance of cooperation among three key sectors: universities, industry, and government, to promote innovation ([C1125] (Faisal et al., 2017), [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019)). It argues that an innovation-driven economy is promoted when these three sectors work together, contributing to the development of new technologies and their commercialization [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019). This model encourages sustainable knowledge transfer processes. [E066] (Pereira and Franco, 2023) stresses the importance of formal and informal cooperation channels, which can improve regional competitiveness by complementing local production frameworks. The authors examine how these interactions can transform the region's social structure [E066] (Pereira and Franco, 2023).
- **Open innovation framework:** Promotes external knowledge exchange between universities and companies ([C1047] (Jugend et al., 2020)). Balancing intellectual property with open access is essential. Unlike the traditional linear model, the open innovation model encourages universities to collaborate with external partners, such as industry and research institutions, fostering a bidirectional flow of knowledge and technologies. Therefore, universities are not only producers of knowledge, but also recipients and adapters of external insights [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019).

Table 9
Summary of anti-patterns categories

Challenges	Grounded	Density
Mismatch between industry and academia	129	11
Lack of training, experience, and skills	77	4
Low, lack or drop of interest	74	5
Communication-related issues	63	4
Human and Organizational Factors	22	5
Solution and method applicability	82	5
Management-related issues	13	7
Resource-related issues	142	10
Contractual Concerns	20	4
Privacy Issues	14	2
Lack of research relevance	68	1

- **Project-based models:** Focus on structured, time-bound, specific goal-oriented collaborations ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)). Dependency on mutual trust and resource allocation. Emphasize applied research, knowledge transfer, and mutual benefits for both parties.

4.5. RQ5: What specific activities, strategies, and practices support IAC implementation in SE?

This question aims to identify and present strategies and practices that promote successful partnerships. We will also examine the obstacles and complexities that must be addressed to achieve synergy between these communities.

4.5.1. Anti-patterns (challenges):

After the analysis, 25 categories (codes) were identified, and, in sequence, the groundedness (quantity of citations) and density (amount of association with other codes, as observed in the networks) for each were verified. In total, 11 antipatterns were identified and shown in Table 9. In this section, each challenge is detailed.

- **Incompatibility/mismatch between industry and academia:** Collaboration between academia and industry is often hindered by misaligned objectives, timelines, and cultures. Academia focuses on theoretical exploration, long-term knowledge development, and publications, while industry prioritizes practical, commercially viable solutions with immediate return on investment (ROI) ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)). Industry demand for rapid results contrasts with the academic approach of slow and thorough research processes, leading to frustration ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022), [B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Faculty responsibilities, such as teaching, further limit academic involvement in industry projects ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)). Bridging this gap requires strategies such as student and employee exchange programs to foster mutual understanding and align goals ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). Improved communication and collaborative frameworks can enhance the effectiveness of these partnerships.
- **Lack of training, experience, and skills:** Lack of training and skills in collaborative projects can be addressed by promoting interactive spaces such as workshops and forums to facilitate knowledge exchange between researchers and practitioners ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)). Hands-on Agile training improves student preparedness for teamwork and industry roles ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022)) while emphasizing soft skills such as communication and project management, aligning SE education with the collaborative demands of the industry ([A232] (Cico et al., 2021)). In addition, targeted workshops on Agile methods and real-world tools improve collaboration and productivity in project environments ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)).
- **Low, lack, or drop of interest/commitment:** Low interest or commitment to collaborative projects often stems from weak relationships and a lack of participant trust. (Garousi et al., 2016) ([A238]) suggests that sustainable partnerships - focused on long-term relationships rather than short-term project-specific collaborations - can mitigate this issue. By fostering a deeper understanding of each partner's needs and expectations, participants are more likely to remain engaged and motivated.

Furthermore, trust-building initiatives, as highlighted by (Garousi et al., 2016) ([A238]), play a critical role in maintaining interest and commitment. Positive and frequent interactions over time strengthen trust and

enhance collaboration efficiency and satisfaction. These measures ensure people feel valued and invested in the partnership's success, reducing dropout rates and improving project outcomes.

- **Communication related:** Communication issues in collaborative projects often arise due to limited interactions and differing priorities between academia and industry. Garousi et al. ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)) highlight that a lack of regular engagement reduces opportunities for knowledge transfer and joint problem-solving, creating barriers to effective collaboration. Furthermore, Garousi et al. ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)) identify differences in language, work practices, and priorities as key contributors to communication breakdowns, which can hinder project progress and mutual understanding.

Ankrah et al. ([B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)) emphasize that successful collaboration relies heavily on effective communication and coordination. Poor communication can lead to misunderstandings, misaligned goals, and delays, ultimately jeopardizing the success of collaborative efforts. Addressing these challenges requires fostering regular interactions, aligning stakeholder priorities, and establishing clear communication channels to enhance mutual understanding and project outcomes.

Bjarnason et al. (2021) conducted a case study on communication gaps in joint software engineering projects, identifying facilitators such as the relevance of the research and frequent communication that help bridge gaps and improve collaboration outcomes, underscoring the importance of communication in overcoming knowledge mismatches between academia and industry (Rico, Bjarnason, Engström, Höst and Runeson, 2021).

- **Human and organizational factors:** (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015) ([B484]) identifies misaligned priorities and cultural differences as a recurring issue. Human and managerial aspects, particularly cultural and value disparities, significantly challenge collaborative projects between academia and industry. (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019) ([A081]) highlights that differences in culture, language, and values often lead to misunderstandings, complicating joint efforts. Similarly, (Garousi et al., 2016) ([A238]) emphasizes that distinct organizational cultures and expectations across the two sectors can lead to misaligned goals and friction.

(Brings et al., 2018) ([B077]) point out that differences in work culture, operational pace, and organizational priorities further exacerbate these challenges, which impact the effectiveness of collaborative initiatives. (Maresova et al., 2019) ([E062]) specifically notes the divergent goals of academia and industry: academia focuses on long-term research objectives, while industry prioritizes short-term, profit-oriented outcomes. Aligning these priorities requires deliberate efforts to bridge cultural divides and establish mutual understanding, fostering successful collaborations.

- **Solution and method applicability:** Encourage empirical and applied research, focusing on solving tangible problems through case studies, user studies, and fieldwork. ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)).
- **Management-related issues:** Management-related issues in collaborative projects stem from misaligned timelines, with academia and industry often operating on different schedules, creating tension over deadlines ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019)). Leadership support is critical, as a lack of commitment can affect resources, motivation, and commitment to collaboration (Sherman et al., 2018). Faculty autonomy also plays an important role, and academics favor partnerships that allow intellectual freedom and align with their research goals, while rigid industry-driven objectives can deter participation ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)). Motivational factors, such as applying research in real-world settings or accessing funding, further influence commitment ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)).
- **Resource-related issues:** (Zhuang and Shi, 2024) ([E465]) discuss resource imbalances that affect collaborations. Resource-related issues in collaborative projects arise from the funding, staffing, and time constraints faced by both academia and industry ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022)). Resource imbalances, in which industry partners have greater access to tools and infrastructure, further strain project dynamics ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). Funding shortages and under-resourced Technology Transfer Offices hinder technology transfer and commercialization efforts ([B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Although faculty expertise is a critical resource for industry, misaligned academic incentive structures often reduce motivation for collaboration ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)). The substantial resource commitments required for partnerships can also strain both universities and industry partners ([B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)).

Table 10
Summary of patterns categories

Patterns	Grounded	Density
Knowledge management	17	8
Stakeholders engagement	126	16
Industry needs	41	8
Solving relevant problems	14	6
Maintaining relationships	89	13
Software methodology	75	17
Teamwork	27	9
Manage Risks and Limitations	13	2
Researcher's access	14	5
Academic rigor	45	9
Funding and contracting	57	0
Cultural awareness	95	12
Project management	4	0
Technology transfer	197	2

- Contractual concern:** Legal concerns in collaborative projects often stem from disputes for commercialization, licensing terms, and regulations, which can hinder progress if not addressed ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgrubber, 2019), [B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013)). Universities face challenges in balancing innovation protection with academic openness while negotiating fair agreements and navigating complex legal frameworks ([B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Confidentiality constraints arise as industry partners prioritize data security while academia emphasizes openness, leading to potential conflicts over data access and publication rights ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). Ethical concerns, such as privacy and data security during industry experiments, further complicate collaborations ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)). Clear contractual terms and robust intellectual property policies are essential to mitigate these challenges and foster effective partnerships.
- Privacy concern:** Balance between proprietary rights and open innovation frameworks ([C1322] (Arenas and González, 2018)). Privacy concerns in collaborative projects arise from issues related to intellectual property (IP) rights, data security, and confidentiality. Low trust can hinder information sharing, while complex negotiations over IP ownership and data handling can limit collaboration ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018), [B238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). Disputes over research outputs and commercialization rights often require clear agreements to prevent conflicts ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)). Establishing confidentiality protocols and clear IP policies fosters trust, ensuring secure information exchange and successful partnerships ([E147] (Wijesinghe, Hansson, Ekenberg and Hettiarachchi, 2020)).
- Lack of research relevance:** Collaborative projects between academia and industry often lack relevance due to different priorities and measures of success. Academia focuses on theoretical knowledge and publications, while industry values practical, hands-on experience and ROI ([A232] (Cico et al., 2021), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). This disconnect limits the applicability of academic research to real-world challenges ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)). Aligning goals, incorporating practical experiences, and establishing shared success metrics can help enhance the relevance and impact of these collaborations.

4.5.2. Patterns (best practices):

Collaborative research, often involving multiple teams and multifaceted projects, requires a set of best practices to ensure its success. Through our analysis of secondary studies, we have identified 14 best-practice categories, as described in Table 10.

- Knowledge management (communication, training, and skills):** Effective knowledge management, which encompasses communication, training, and skill development, plays a crucial role in the success of collaborative projects between academia and industry ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)). (Nsanzumuhire and Groot, 2020)([E375]) discuss how communication reduces conflicts. Industry highly values practical, hands-on experience, often gained through real-world projects, while many academic programs still emphasize theoretical

knowledge with limited practical application ([A232] (Cico et al., 2021)). This gap highlights the need for targeted training and for better integration of practical experience into academic settings. Clear communication and alignment of goals are also essential, as differing success metrics -such as academic publications versus industry ROI - can hinder collaboration and limit the perceived practical relevance of research ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). Bridging these gaps can enhance knowledge transfer and improve outcomes in joint projects.

- **Stakeholders engagement (ensuring engagement, commitment, and project management):** Effective knowledge management in collaborative projects between academia and industry is based on clear communication, targeted training, and leveraging skills. Open and consistent communication is vital for aligning expectations, building trust, and bridging gaps between partners ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019), [A164] (Marques et al., 2022), [A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Faculty members play a key role as 'intellectual capital', translating academic research into industry-relevant applications and bridging knowledge gaps ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)). Universities can further strengthen collaborations by improving communication channels, particularly with small and medium enterprises, ensuring that research has practical applications that drive competitiveness ([E084] (Pereira and Franco, 2022)). These measures foster impactful partnerships that align academic expertise with industry needs and objectives.
- **Industry needs (challenges, goals, and problems):** Successful collaborative projects between academia and industry depend on aligning goals, addressing industry-specific challenges, and fostering mutual benefits. Misaligned objectives often arise as academia prioritizes theoretical contributions and publishing, while industry focuses on practical problem-solving outcomes ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)). Early clear agreements on project objectives and deliverables are crucial to avoid misunderstandings and ensure that the goals of both sides are met ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [E144] (Ford et al., 2021)). Faculty with expertise closely aligned with industry needs enhance the likelihood of successful knowledge transfer and innovation, highlighting the importance of strategic collaboration ([B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015), [B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013)). Shared vision, open communication, and structured feedback loops throughout the project lifecycle foster alignment and ensure practical and impactful results ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019), [E144] (Ford et al., 2021), [E375] (Nsanzumuhire and Groot, 2020)).
- **Solving relevant problems (ensuring benefits for the industry):** To ensure benefits for the industry and solve pertinent problems of collaborative projects, it is necessary to focus on practical challenges in the real world and provide actionable insights. Industry professionals value research that incorporates case studies, field experiments, and empirical methods, as it directly addresses their needs ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Studies of Agile methods in real-world settings exemplify how academics can align their work with industry practices to improve relevance and impact ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022)). Industry-based experiments often prioritize improvements in decision-making and business performance, focusing on immediate, practical applications over theoretical insights ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)). These approaches foster stronger collaboration by demonstrating clear value to industry partners.
- **Maintaining relationships (mutual respect, understanding, and appreciation):** Maintaining strong relationships, mutual respect, understanding, and gratitude are essential for successful collaborative projects between academia and industry. Trust plays a central role, fostering open communication, risk-sharing, and resource exchange while reducing fears of exploitation or misuse of knowledge ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018), [B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Long-term partnerships are particularly effective in building trust and enabling a productive exchange of knowledge since repeated interactions strengthen mutual understanding and respect ([B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015), [B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013)). Establishing clear communication channels and valuing each partner's expertise and contributions further promotes cooperation and innovation ([A484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015), [E144] (Ford et al., 2021)). Additionally, leveraging both formal agreements and informal connections can enhance collaboration by aligning shared goals and creating a supportive organizational climate ([E463] (Singh and Kaundal, 2022), [A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019)).
- **Software methodology (be agile):** Incorporating software methodologies, particularly Agile practices, into collaborative projects fosters the adoption of industry-relevant good practices and enhances the practical value of research. Agile methods are a shared interest for both academia and industry, with collaborations enabling

academics to test concepts in real-world settings and adapt practices to diverse contexts ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022)). Such partnerships help bridge the gap between theoretical exploration and practical application, with academia contributing innovative ideas and industry providing environments for empirical testing ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020), [B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)). Although industry experiments often use quasi-experimental designs due to real-world constraints, these methods still provide actionable insights that drive improvements in Agile and related practices ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)). By integrating Agile methodologies into academic curricula, universities better prepare students for industry demands, further strengthening collaborative outcomes ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022)).

- **Teamwork (involving the “right” practitioners):** Effective teamwork is critical to the success of collaborative projects, especially in Agile environments. A positive organizational climate with aligned goals fosters mutual understanding, ensuring that the objectives of both partners are met and enhancing collaboration effectiveness ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018)). Involving practitioners who are open to learning and sharing knowledge creates a learning environment that promotes skill development and facilitates knowledge transfer between academia and industry ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018)). Practical project-based learning opportunities, such as internships and joint projects, improve participants’ readiness for real-world challenges and strengthen collaboration outcomes ([A232] (Cico et al., 2021)). In addition, securing the support of key stakeholders is essential, as their participation helps mitigate disruptions and align roles to ensure project success ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)).
- **Manage Risks and Limitations:** Considering and managing risks and limitations is essential for the success of Agile collaborative projects. High-stakes projects benefit from fair risk sharing and effective management of complexity to ensure mutual trust and commitment ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019)). Time constraints often pose challenges, as academic research timelines are generally longer and may not align with the rapid delivery expectations of industry projects ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016)). Additionally, industry experiments frequently face limitations in terms of time, budget, and personnel, which can restrict the scope and depth of studies, necessitating efficient prioritization and resource allocation ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)).
- **Researcher’s access (on-site presence):** The On-site presence of researchers in industry settings significantly improves the relevance and applicability of academic research by ensuring alignment with real-world challenges. Establishing joint projects and maintaining regular communication channels facilitates the identification of industry-specific problems, enabling researchers to tailor their efforts toward practical solutions. This direct interaction fosters mutual understanding, bridges the gap between theoretical exploration and practical application, and supports the agile adaptation of research goals to industry needs ([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)).
- **Academic rigor (Follow a research/data collection method or guidelines on the selection of research methods):** Academic rigor is essential for producing high-quality research that meets the needs of both academia and industry. By combining theoretical knowledge and structured research methodologies from academia with practical expertise from industry, we can foster innovation and create mutual benefits. However, some studies lack methodological transparency, which limits their replicability and the applicability of their findings in real-world settings. Balancing scientific rigor with industry emphasis on practical outcomes is crucial to ensure successful collaboration. Designing research models that respect academic freedom while aligning with industry goals can enhance faculty engagement and ensure that research efforts result in robust evidence-based outcomes that benefit all stakeholders ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019), [B198] (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015), [B482] (Dieste et al., 2013), [E144] (Ford et al., 2021)).
- **Funding and contracting (recruiting, partnerships and privacy):** Public funding and intermediary entities play a crucial role in facilitating these partnerships by providing financial support and fostering connections ([C1047] (Jugend et al., 2020), [C1125] (Faisal et al., 2017)). Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and innovation centers offer essential guidance on intellectual property, project management, and legal frameworks, ensuring smoother collaborations ([B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013), [E062] (Maresova et al., 2019)). Universities benefit from flexible IP policies and entrepreneurial support structures, which attract industry partners and enhance commercialization efforts ([B276] (Perkmann et al., 2013), [B484] (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)). However, funding restrictions, bureaucratic hurdles, and different priorities between academia and industry remain significant barriers ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [E463] (Singh and Kaundal, 2022)). Addressing these

challenges requires strategic policies, infrastructure investment, and alignment of goals to maximize mutual benefits.

- **Cultural Awareness (understand the context, constraints, and language):** Cultural awareness is essential for successful academic-industry collaborations, as it bridges the operational and priority differences between the two sectors. Academia often emphasizes theoretical exploration, while industry focuses on practical, commercially viable solutions, making alignment challenging ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018)). Understanding the unique context and constraints of each partner, such as the complexities of maintaining experimental rigor in dynamic software development environments, is vital for effective collaboration ([B482] (Dieste et al., 2013)). Companies benefit from academic insight to adapt methodologies like Agile to their specific cultural and operational needs, fostering mutual understanding and enhancing project outcomes ([A164] (Marques et al., 2022)).
- **Project management (efficient research):** Effective research project management in collaborative projects requires a balance of influence in decision-making to ensure mutual investment and commitment of all partners ([A081] (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019)). Supportive leadership is essential for creating a positive collaborative climate, reducing friction from different organizational cultures, and motivating meaningful engagement ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018)). Appointing dedicated liaisons or "champions" within each organization can streamline communication, address challenges proactively, and bridge gaps between academic and industry partners, fostering smoother collaboration and effective knowledge transfer ([A238] (Garousi et al., 2016), [B077] (Brings et al., 2018)).
- **Technology Transfer:** Effective technology transfer in collaborative projects bridges the gap between theoretical research and industry applications. Approaches such as collaborative R&D, prototyping, and demonstration projects enable academia to make new software engineering techniques accessible and relevant to practitioners ([B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Student projects, internships, and training workshops further facilitate hands-on knowledge exchange and skill development ([B077] (Brings et al., 2018)). Encouraging innovation and learning environments fosters continuous improvement and idea sharing, which are essential for successful collaboration ([A217] (Sherman et al., 2018)). Aligning academic incentives with industry goals, such as rewarding commercialization and patents, increases the likelihood of significant technology transfer ([E062] (Maresova et al., 2019)). Furthermore, publishing research findings in accessible outlets ensures broader industry participation and adoption of research results([A078] (Garousi et al., 2020)).

5. Discussion

This systematic tertiary literature review examined the current state of collaborative projects between industry and academia, with a specific focus on the global software engineering field. To achieve this, 30 secondary studies were analyzed to provide an overview of the discussions in this area, addressing five key research questions.

This section summarizes the key findings and highlights their implications for professionals and researchers in the software development industry.

Figure 6 illustrates the interconnections between key challenges and mitigation strategies in academia-industry collaborations, emphasizing the role of management issues as a central factor. Commitment issues arising from a mismatch between partners contribute to management difficulties, while communication issues exacerbate these challenges. Insufficient training, experience, skills, resistance to change, and inflexible practices also hinder effective collaboration. These issues can be mitigated through strategies such as conducting seminars and workshops, leveraging existing knowledge from both sectors, fostering social networking, improving researcher communication, and engaging champions to advocate for change. Furthermore, administrative support is essential in addressing structural and commitment-related challenges, underscoring the importance of proactive management interventions to improve the efficiency and sustainability of collaborations.

- **Types of Collaborative Activities:** Promote student projects and internships to provide hands-on experience and develop industry-ready talent with Agile expertise. Engage in joint research projects to address real-world challenges and advance knowledge (Marques et al., 2022). Involve industry in curriculum development to align academic programs with practical needs (Marques et al., 2022).

Figure 6: Management issues network.

- **Strategic Alignment:** Establish clear goals and expectations to align partners' objectives and reduce conflicts (Sherman et al., 2018). Develop climate assessments to identify organizational misalignments before collaboration (Sherman et al., 2018).
- **Trust and Leadership:** Foster trust through regular communication, transparency, and fair IP agreements (Sherman et al., 2018). Ensure leadership involvement to allocate resources and support collaborations effectively (Sherman et al., 2018).
- **Technology Transfer:** Align academic research with industry needs for practical relevance and successful adoption (Brings et al., 2018). Develop clear IP agreements and confidentiality protocols to avoid disputes (Brings et al., 2018). Build long-term relationships to promote trust and mutual understanding (Brings et al., 2018).
- **Policy and Institutional Support:** Encourage academic involvement by recognizing it in performance evaluations (Perkmann et al., 2013). Train researchers in commercialization and entrepreneurial skills (Perkmann et al., 2013). Support flexible policies and TTOs to facilitate collaborations and IP negotiations (Perkmann et al., 2013).
- **Improving Industry Experiments:** Adopt rigorous methodologies, standardized reporting, and long-term studies to improve the experimental reliability (Dieste et al., 2013). Foster collaboration between academia and industry to bring methodological rigor to applied studies (Dieste et al., 2013).

- **Collaboration Benefits and Mechanisms:** Universities gain funding, enhanced research impact, and reputation, while industries access cutting-edge knowledge and innovation (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015). Use joint research centers, innovation hubs, and intermediaries to structure and facilitate partnerships (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015). Governments should provide incentives, funding, and policy frameworks to promote collaboration (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015).

Implementing these recommendations can help stakeholders overcome common challenges, build sustainable partnerships, and maximize the impact of academia-industry collaborations.

6. Threats to Validity

This section discusses potential threats to the results of the tertiary literature review. Following this overview, we will outline the actions to minimize these biases. To analyze these threats, we adopted the guidelines proposed by (Petersen et al., 2015; Runeson and Höst, 2009), which include descriptive validity, theoretical validity, interpretive validity, and repeatability.

6.1. Internal Validity

This thread of validity refers to the degree of causality of the conclusions drawn from the extracted data. Potential issues and limitations can arise during the selection process, including (1) research carried out by two primary researchers, with the assistance of two additional researchers who supported data validation; (2) searches carried out in five main automated databases without extending the searches to manual databases; and (3) the need to adapt the search string for each data repository, as each repository has its unique search processes. Also, to ensure the integrity of the findings, the Risk of Bias (RoB) was rigorously assessed for each secondary study. This evaluation was conducted independently by two primary reviewers using a structured appraisal protocol. In instances where scoring discrepancies arose, a senior supervisor acted as an arbitrator to review the points of contention and facilitate a final consensus. This process was integral to the study's inclusion logic: any papers identified as having a high risk of bias—specifically those scoring below the established 50% threshold on the quality criteria—were systematically excluded from the final synthesis. This stringent filtering mechanism was implemented to prevent the dilution of evidence by low-quality data and to ensure that the resulting conclusions are anchored in robust methodological foundations.

6.2. Construction Validity

Concerns regarding construct validity in our study relate to the suitability of the research questions and the categorization scheme used for data extraction. The authors maintained a clear connection between the research goals and the questions addressed using the categorization scheme. This scheme was developed according to established guidelines for systematic literature mapping and review studies (Kitchenham et al., 2009; Perkmann and Walsh, 2009).

6.3. Reliability

Concerns about this replication of research. To maintain transparency in our process, we provide our research protocol. This protocol includes the following elements: (1) the search terms and their explanations; (2) the search engines utilized; (3) the period for the search; (4) the search protocol detailing the metadata used; and (5) the criteria to include or exclude studies.

6.4. External Validity

Related to the generality of the results (Elberzhager, Münch and Nha, 2012), we acknowledge that empirical evidence in SE can be cross-pollinated with the IS community. One limitation of our findings' scope is the exclusion of grey literature. This choice stems from our research design, which prioritizes peer-reviewed secondary literature to provide a consolidated view of high-quality evidence. Consequently, while some emerging industrial practices might be underrepresented, the reliability of the synthesized taxonomy is strengthened by the academic rigor of the primary sources analyzed.

7. Conclusions

Collaborative projects between industry and academia in software engineering offer an opportunity to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical application. These partnerships have the potential to foster innovation,

address real-world challenges, and prepare a highly skilled workforce. This tertiary review has explored the current state of the Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC), shedding light on its growing importance and global reach.

Through an extensive analysis of the tertiary literature of significant search engines, we have identified key themes and emerging trends that define these collaborations. The diversity of contributions, which spans countries and institutions worldwide, highlights the shared recognition of IAC as a crucial avenue for advancing the field. In addition, the steady improvement in study quality and the expansion of research topics reflect a dynamic and evolving landscape.

Although collaborative projects face challenges, such as aligning goals and navigating resource constraints, the increasing volume of publications on IAC demonstrates a commitment to overcoming these hurdles. Our findings provide actionable information and practical recommendations to help researchers, educators, and practitioners strengthen their partnerships. By addressing existing gaps and building on lessons learned, these collaborations can drive progress in academia and industry, ensuring mutual growth and success.

This review presents the current state of IAC in software engineering and provides guidance for future endeavors. By fostering stronger connections and embracing shared goals, we can amplify the impact of these partnerships and make meaningful contributions to advancing the field.

Current research findings reveal that while the ‘what’ of collaboration is relatively well documented, the ‘how’—particularly with regard to scaling and sustaining IAC initiatives—remains insufficiently addressed. The main conclusion of this study is that successful IAC in SE requires moving beyond isolated, ad-hoc projects towards more integrated collaboration ecosystems in which tool support and formal knowledge-sharing mechanisms play a central role. The review provides an initial foundation for developing context-aware, outcome-oriented collaboration frameworks that can be refined and extended in future research

Future work on industry-academic collaboration (IAC) in software engineering should focus on several key areas to deepen understanding and improve the effectiveness of these partnerships. First, longitudinal studies are necessary to assess the long-term effects of collaborative projects on academic and industrial outcomes, including innovation, workforce development, and technological advancements. Second, more research should compare countries and regions, which would also be valuable for understanding how different policy frameworks, funding mechanisms, and cultural factors affect the success of collaboration.

Lastly, research on new collaboration models, such as hybrid approaches combining virtual and in-person interactions, could offer practical insights into overcoming logistical and resource constraints. By addressing these areas, future work can help ensure that IAC remains a robust and adaptable mechanism for advancing software engineering.

A. Appendix: Accepted Studies: Tertiary Review

A.1. Automatic Search

- [A238] Garousi, Vahid, Kai Petersen, and Baris Ozkan. *Challenges and best practices in industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review*. Information and Software Technology 79 (2016): 106-127. (Garousi et al., 2016)
- [A078] Garousi, Vahid, Markus Borg, and Markku Oivo. *Practical relevance of software engineering research: synthesizing the community’s voice*. Empirical Software Engineering 25 (2020): 1687-1754. (Garousi et al., 2020)
- [A081] Rybnicek, Robert, and Roland Königsgruber. *What makes industry–university collaboration succeed? A systematic review of the literature*. Journal of business economics 89.2 (2019): 221-250. (Rybnicek and Königsgruber, 2019)
- [A164] de Gois Marques, Denis, et al. *Industry-academy collaboration in agile methodology: a systematic literature review*. 2022 17th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI). IEEE, 2022. (Marques et al., 2022)
- [A217] Sherman, Sofia, Irit Hadar, and Gil Luria. *Leveraging organizational climate theory for understanding industry-academia collaboration*. Information and Software Technology 98 (2018): 148-160. (Sherman et al., 2018)

- [A232] Cico, Orges, et al. *Exploring the intersection between software industry and Software Engineering education-A systematic mapping of Software Engineering Trends*. Journal of Systems and Software 172 (2021): 110736. (Cico et al., 2021)

A.2. Snowballing - Round 1:

- [B077] Brings, Jennifer, et al. "Approaches, success factors, and barriers for technology transfer in software engineering—Results of a systematic literature review." Journal of Software: Evolution and Process 30.11 (2018): e1981. (Brings et al., 2018)
- [B198] Boardman, C., & Bozeman, B. (2015). *Academic faculty as intellectual property in university-industry research alliances*. Economics of Innovation and New Technology, 24(5), 403-420. (Boardman and Bozeman, 2015)
- [B276] Perkmann, M., Tartari, V., McKelvey, M., Autio, E., Broström, A., D'este, P., ... & Sobrero, M. (2013). *Academic engagement and commercialisation: A review of the literature on university–industry relations*. Research policy, 42(2), 423-442. (Perkmann et al., 2013)
- [B482] Dieste, O., Juristo, N., & Martínez, M. D. (2013, May). *Software industry experiments: A systematic literature review*. In 2013 1st International Workshop on Conducting Empirical Studies in Industry (CESI) (pp. 2-8). IEEE. (Dieste et al., 2013)
- [B484] Ankrah, S., & Omar, A. T. (2015). *Universities–industry collaboration: A systematic review*. Scandinavian journal of management, 31(3), 387-408. (Ankrah and AL-Tabbaa, 2015)
- [E062] Maresova, P., Stemberkova, R., & Fadeyi, O. (2019). *Models, processes, and roles of universities in technology transfer management: A systematic review*. Administrative Sciences, 9(3), 67. (Maresova et al., 2019)
- [E066] Pereira, R., & Franco, M. (2023). *University-firm cooperation and regional development: proposal of a model of analysis*. Journal of the Knowledge Economy, 14(2), 676-690. (Pereira and Franco, 2023)
- [E084] Pereira, R., & Franco, M. (2022). *Cooperation between universities and SMEs: A systematic literature review*. Industry and Higher Education, 36(1), 37-50. (Pereira and Franco, 2022)
- [E092] Figueiredo, N., & Fernandes, C. (2020). *Cooperation university–industry: A systematic literature review*. International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management, 17(08), 2130001. (Figueiredo and Fernandes, 2020)
- [E116] Pesti, C., Tamášová, V., Lajčín, D., & Bodonyi, E. (2021). *University-Industry Collaboration as a driver for innovation in Europe - A literature review with a systematic approach*. Ad Alta: Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, 11(2). (PESTI et al., 2021)
- [E144] Ford, K. L., Portz, J. D., Zhou, S., Gornail, S., Moore, S. L., Zhang, X., & Bull, S. (2021). *Benefits, facilitators, and recommendations for digital health academic-industry collaboration: a mini review*. Frontiers in Digital Health, 3, 616278. (Ford et al., 2021)
- [E147] Wijesinghe, C., Hansson, H., Ekenberg, L., & Hettiarachchi, E. (2020). *Influential Factors for ICT Innovations in Sri Lanka University-Industry Collaboration: A Systematic Literature Review*. Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education, 47-66. (Wijesinghe et al., 2020)
- [E375] Nsanzumuhire, S. U., & Groot, W. (2020). *Context perspective on University-Industry Collaboration processes: A systematic review of literature*. Journal of cleaner production, 258, 120861. (Nsanzumuhire and Groot, 2020)
- [E463] Singh, S., & Kaundal, B. (2022). *Academia-industry linkages: Theoretical and empirical review article*. World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 15(1), 104-115. (Singh and Kaundal, 2022)
- [E465] Zhuang, T., & Shi, J. (2024). *Engagement, determinants and challenges: A multinational systematic review of education-focused university-industry collaborations*. Educational Review, 76(5), 1363-1391. (Zhuang and Shi, 2024)

A.3. Snowballing - Round 2:

- [C1047] Jugend, D., Fiorini, P. D. C., Armellini, F., & Ferrari, A. G. (2020). *Public support for innovation: A systematic review of the literature and implications for open innovation*. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 156, 119985. (Jugend et al., 2020)
- [C1125] Faisal, R., Chong, A. L., & Yee, A. S. V. (2017). *Systematic review of sustainable knowledge transfer process in government-industry-academia consortium*. *Asian Journal of Innovation and Policy*, 6(3), 295-312. (Faisal et al., 2017)
- [C1322] Arenas, J. J., & González, D. *Technology transfer models and elements in the University-Industry collaboration*. *Administrative sciences*. 2018; 8 (2): 19. (Arenas and González, 2018)
- [C1352] Good, M., Knockaert, M., Soppe, B., & Wright, M. (2019). *The technology transfer ecosystem in academia. An organizational design perspective*. *Technovation*, 82, 35-50. (Good et al., 2019)
- [F009] Ghanadinezhad, F. & Ghane, M. R. (2024) *Analyzing Review Studies and Bibliometrics of University-Industry Interaction Using Scoping Review*. *International Journal of Information Science and Management (IJISM)*; 22(3): 85-110. (Ghanadinezhad and Ghane, 2024)
- [F081] Mascarenhas C., Ferreira J. J. & Marques C. (2018) *University–industry cooperation: A systematic literature review and research agenda*. *Science and Public Policy*, Volume 45, Issue 5, Pages 708–718. (Mascarenhas, Ferreira and Marques, 2018)
- [F125] Rossoni, A.L., Vasconcellos, E.P.G. & Rossoni, R.L.C. (2024) *Barriers and facilitators of university-industry collaboration for research, development and innovation: a systematic review*. *Manag Rev Q* 74, 1841–1877. (Rossoni, de Vasconcellos and de Castilho Rossoni, 2024)
- [F394] Bastos E. C., Sengik A. R., Gamarra J. T. (2021) *Fifty years of University-industry collaboration: a global bibliometrics overview*. *Science and Public Policy*, Volume 48, Issue 2, Pages 177–199. (Bastos, Sengik and Tello-Gamarra, 2021)
- [F826] Cohen, M., Fernandes, G. & Godinho, P. (2024) *Measuring the impacts of university-industry R&D collaborations: a systematic literature review*. *J Technol Transf.* (Cohen, Fernandes and Godinho, 2024)

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References

- Ankrah, S., AL-Tabbaa, O., 2015. Universities–industry collaboration: A systematic review. *Scandinavian Journal of Management* 31, 387–408. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0956522115000238>, doi:10.1016/j.scaman.2015.02.003.
- Arenas, J.J., González, D., 2018. Technology transfer models and elements in the university-industry collaboration. *Administrative sciences* 8, 19.
- Aria, M., Cuccurullo, C., 2017. bibliometrix: An r-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis. *Journal of informetrics* 11, 959–975.
- Bamford, D., 2024. How industry-academia collaborations create impact. AACSB Insights URL: <https://www.aacsb.edu/insights/articles/2024/11/how-industry-academia-collaborations-create-impact>. accessed 16 Feb 2026.
- Barnes, T., Pashby, I., Gibbons, A., 2002. Effective university–industry interaction:: A multi-case evaluation of collaborative r&d projects. *European management journal* 20, 272–285.
- Bastos, E.C., Sengik, A.R., Tello-Gamarra, J., 2021. Fifty years of university-industry collaboration: a global bibliometrics overview. *Science and Public Policy* 48, 177–199. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scaa077>, doi:10.1093/scipol/scaa077.
- Boardman, C., Bozeman, B., 2015. Academic faculty as intellectual property in university-industry research alliances. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology* 24, 403–420.
- Brereton, P., Kitchenham, B.A., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Khalil, M., 2007. Lessons from applying the systematic literature review process within the software engineering domain. *Journal of systems and software* 80, 571–583.
- Brings, J., Daun, M., Brinckmann, S., Keller, K., Weyer, T., 2018. Approaches, success factors, and barriers for technology transfer in software engineering—results of a systematic literature review. *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process* 30, e1981.
- Charmaz, K., 2006. *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*. sage.
- Cico, O., Jaccheri, L., 2019. Industry trends in software engineering education: a systematic mapping study, in: 2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering: Companion Proceedings (ICSE-Companion), IEEE. pp. 292–293.

- Cico, O., Jaccheri, L., Nguyen-Duc, A., Zhang, H., 2021. Exploring the intersection between software industry and software engineering education—a systematic mapping of software engineering trends. *Journal of Systems and Software* 172, 110736.
- Cohen, J., 1968. Weighted kappa: Nominal scale agreement with provision for scaled disagreement or partial credit. *Psychological Bulletin* 70, 213–220. doi:10.1037/h0026256.
- Cohen, M., Fernandes, G., Godinho, P., 2024. Measuring the impacts of university–industry r&d collaborations: a systematic literature review. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 1–30.
- Dallegre, T., Santos, W.B., 2023. Action research for industry academia collaboration: A replication study, in: 2023 18th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI), IEEE. pp. 1–6.
- Dallegre, T., Vasconcelos, G., Alves, G., Santos, W., 2021. Are we ready? identifying the gap between academia and software industry in the context of agile methodologies, in: *Anais do XXXII Simposio Brasileiro de Informatica na Educaçao*, SBC. pp. 35–47.
- Dieste, O., Juristo, N., Martínez, M.D., 2013. Software industry experiments: A systematic literature review, in: 2013 1st International Workshop on Conducting Empirical Studies in Industry (CESI), IEEE. pp. 2–8.
- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, D., Pandey, N., Lim, W.M., 2021. How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of business research* 133, 285–296.
- Dyba, T., Dingsoyr, T., Hanssen, G.K., 2007. Applying systematic reviews to diverse study types: An experience report, in: *First international symposium on empirical software engineering and measurement (ESEM 2007)*, IEEE. pp. 225–234.
- Elberzhager, F., Münch, J., Nha, V.T.N., 2012. A systematic mapping study on the combination of static and dynamic quality assurance techniques. *Information and Software Technology* 54, 1–15.
- Evans, N., Miklosik, A., Du, J.T., 2023. University–industry collaboration as a driver of digital transformation: Types, benefits and enablers. *Heliyon* 9.
- Faisal, R., Chong, A.L., Yee, A.S.V., 2017. Systematic review of sustainable knowledge transfer process in government–industry–academia consortium. *Asian Journal of Innovation and Policy* 6, 295–312.
- Figueiredo, N., Fernandes, C., 2020. Cooperation university–industry: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management* 17, 2130001.
- Ford, K.L., Portz, J.D., Zhou, S., Gornail, S., Moore, S.L., Zhang, X., Bull, S., 2021. Benefits, facilitators, and recommendations for digital health academic–industry collaboration: a mini review. *Frontiers in Digital Health* 3, 616278.
- Garousi, V., Borg, M., Oivo, M., 2020. Practical relevance of software engineering research: synthesizing the community’s voice. *Empirical Software Engineering* 25, 1687–1754.
- Garousi, V., Giray, G., Tuzun, E., 2019a. Understanding the knowledge gaps of software engineers: An empirical analysis based on swebok. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education (TOCE)* 20, 1–33.
- Garousi, V., Giray, G., Tuzun, E., Catal, C., Felderer, M., 2019b. Closing the gap between software engineering education and industrial needs. *IEEE software* 37, 68–77.
- Garousi, V., Petersen, K., Ozkan, B., 2016. Challenges and best practices in industry–academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review. *Information and Software Technology* 79, 106–127.
- Garousi, V., Pfahl, D., Fernandes, J.M., Felderer, M., Mäntylä, M.V., Shepherd, D., Arcuri, A., Coşkunçay, A., Tekinerdogan, B., 2019c. Characterizing industry–academia collaborations in software engineering: evidence from 101 projects. *Empirical Software Engineering* 24, 2540–2602.
- Ghanadinezhad, F., Ghane, M.R., 2024. Analyzing review studies and bibliometrics of university–industry interaction using scoping review 1. *International Journal of Information Science and Management (IJISM)* 22, 85–110. doi:10.22034/ijism.2024.2022906.1400.
- Good, M., Knockaert, M., Soppe, B., Wright, M., 2019. The technology transfer ecosystem in academia. an organizational design perspective. *Technovation* 82, 35–50.
- Hennessy, E.A., Johnson, B.T., Keenan, C., 2019. Best practice guidelines and essential methodological steps to conduct rigorous and systematic meta-reviews. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being* 11, 353–381.
- Jugend, D., Fiorini, P.D.C., Armellini, F., Ferrari, A.G., 2020. Public support for innovation: A systematic review of the literature and implications for open innovation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 156, 119985.
- Keele, S., et al., 2007. Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering.
- Kitchenham, B., 2004. Procedures for performing systematic reviews. *Keele, UK, Keele University* 33, 1–26.
- Kitchenham, B., Brereton, O.P., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Bailey, J., Linkman, S., 2009. Systematic literature reviews in software engineering—a systematic literature review. *Information and software technology* 51, 7–15.
- Kitchenham, B., Pretorius, R., Budgen, D., Brereton, O.P., Turner, M., Niazi, M., Linkman, S., 2010. Systematic literature reviews in software engineering—a tertiary study. *Information and software technology* 52, 792–805.
- Lamprecht, S.J., van Rooyen, G.J., 2012. Models for technology research collaboration between industry and academia in south africa, in: *Proceedings of the 2012 4th IEEE Software Engineering Colloquium (SE)*, pp. 11–17. doi:10.1109/SE.2012.6242350.
- Lima, J.V., Júnior, M.d.M.A., Moya, A., Almeida, R., Anjos, P., Lencastre, M., Fagundes, R.A.d.A.F., Alencar, F., 2019. As metodologias ativas e o ensino em engenharia de software: uma revisão sistemática da literatura, in: *Anais do XXV Workshop de Informática na Escola*, SBC. pp. 1014–1023.
- Lo, D., Nagappan, N., Zimmermann, T., 2015. How practitioners perceive the relevance of software engineering research, in: *Proceedings of the 2015 10th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering*, pp. 415–425.
- Maresova, P., Stemberkova, R., Fadeyi, O., 2019. Models, processes, and roles of universities in technology transfer management: A systematic review. *Administrative Sciences* 9, 67.
- Marijan, D., Gotlieb, A., 2021. Industry–academia research collaboration in software engineering: The certus model. *Information and software technology* 132, 106473.

- Marijan, D., Sen, S., 2022. Industry-academia research collaboration and knowledge co-creation: Patterns and anti-patterns. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 31. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3494519>, doi:10.1145/3494519.
- Marques, D.d.G., Dallegrave, T.D., de Oliveira, C.M., Santos, W.B., 2023. Successful practices in industry-academy collaboration in the context of software agility: A systematic literature review, in: Filipe, J., Śmiełek, M., Brodsky, A., Hammoudi, S. (Eds.), *Enterprise Information Systems*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham. pp. 292–310.
- Marques, D.d.G., Dallegrave, T.L.D.d.A., Barbosa, L.E.L., Rodrigues, C.M.d.O., Santos, W.B., 2022. Industry-academy collaboration in agile methodology: a systematic literature review, in: 2022 17th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI), IEEE. pp. 1–6.
- Mascarenhas, C., Ferreira, J.J., Marques, C., 2018. University-industry cooperation: A systematic literature review and research agenda. *Science and Public Policy* 45, 708–718.
- Muhr, T., 1991. Atlas/ti—a prototype for the support of text interpretation. *Qualitative sociology* 14, 349–371.
- Nsanzumuhire, S.U., Groot, W., 2020. Context perspective on university-industry collaboration processes: A systematic review of literature. *Journal of cleaner production* 258, 120861.
- Page, M.J., McKenzie, J.E., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J.M., Akl, E.A., Brennan, S.E., et al., 2021. The prisma 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *bmj* 372.
- Pereira, R., Franco, M., 2022. Cooperation between universities and smes: A systematic literature review. *Industry and Higher Education* 36, 37–50.
- Pereira, R., Franco, M., 2023. University-firm cooperation and regional development: proposal of a model of analysis. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy* 14, 676–690.
- Perkmann, M., Tartari, V., McKelvey, M., Autio, E., Broström, A., D’este, P., Fini, R., Geuna, A., Grimaldi, R., Hughes, A., et al., 2013. Academic engagement and commercialisation: A review of the literature on university-industry relations. *Research policy* 42, 423–442.
- Perkmann, M., Walsh, K., 2009. The two faces of collaboration: impacts of university-industry relations on public research. *Industrial and Corporate Change* 18, 1033–1065.
- PESTI, C., TAMÁŠOVÁ, V., LAJČIN, D., BODONYI, E., 2021. University-industry collaboration as a drive for innovation in europe—a literature review with a systematic approach. *AD ALTA: Journal of Interdisciplinary Research* 11.
- Petersen, K., Gencel, C., Asghari, N., Baca, D., Betz, S., 2014. Action research as a model for industry-academia collaboration in the software engineering context, in: *Proceedings of the 2014 international workshop on Long-term industrial collaboration on software engineering*, pp. 55–62.
- Petersen, K., Vakkalanka, S., Kuzniarz, L., 2015. Guidelines for conducting systematic mapping studies in software engineering: An update. *Information and Software Technology* 64, 1–18.
- Philbin, S., 2008. Process model for university-industry research collaboration. *European Journal of Innovation Management* .
- Rabiser, R., Schmid, K., Becker, M., Botterweck, G., Galster, M., Groher, I., Weyns, D., 2018. A study and comparison of industrial vs. academic software product line research published at splc, in: *Proceedings of the 22nd International Systems and Software Product Line Conference-Volume 1*, pp. 14–24.
- Rico, S., Bjarnason, E., Engström, E., Höst, M., Runeson, P., 2021. A case study of industry-academia communication in a joint software engineering research project. *Journal of software: Evolution and Process* 33, e2372.
- Rossoni, A.L., de Vasconcellos, E.P.G., de Castilho Rossoni, R.L., 2024. Barriers and facilitators of university-industry collaboration for research, development and innovation: a systematic review. *Management Review Quarterly* 74, 1841–1877.
- Runeson, P., Höst, M., 2009. Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering. *Empirical software engineering* 14, 131–164.
- Rybnicek, R., Königsgruber, R., 2019. What makes industry-university collaboration succeed? a systematic review of the literature. *Journal of business economics* 89, 221–250.
- Sandberg, A., Pareto, L., Arts, T., 2011. Agile collaborative research: Action principles for industry-academia collaboration. *IEEE software* 28, 74–83.
- Sherman, S., Hadar, I., Luria, G., 2018. Leveraging organizational climate theory for understanding industry-academia collaboration. *Information and Software Technology* 98, 148–160.
- Singh, S., Kaundal, B., 2022. Academia-industry linkages: Theoretical and empirical review article. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 15, 104–115.
- Ursić, L., Baldacchino, G., Bašić, Ž., Sainz, A.B., Buljan, I., Hampel, M., Kružić, I., Majić, M., Marušić, A., Thetiot, F., et al., 2022. Factors influencing interdisciplinary research and industry-academia collaborations at six european universities: A qualitative study. *Sustainability* 14, 9306.
- Wijesinghe, C., Hansson, H., Ekenberg, L., Hettiarachchi, E., 2020. Influential factors for ict innovations in sri lanka university-industry collaboration: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education* , 47–66.
- Wohlin, C., 2014. Guidelines for snowballing in systematic literature studies and a replication in software engineering, in: *Proceedings of the 18th international conference on evaluation and assessment in software engineering*, pp. 1–10.
- Wohlin, C., Aurum, A., Angelis, L., Phillips, L., Dittrich, Y., Gorschek, T., Grahn, H., Henningsson, K., Kagstrom, S., Low, G., Rovegard, P., Tomaszewski, P., van Toorn, C., Winter, J., 2012. The success factors powering industry-academia collaboration. *IEEE Softw.* 29, 67–73.
- Wohlin, C., Aurum, A., Angelis, L., Phillips, L., Dittrich, Y., Gorschek, T., Grahn, H., Henningsson, K., Kagstrom, S., Low, G., et al., 2011. The success factors powering industry-academia collaboration. *IEEE software* 29, 67–73.
- Zhang, H., Babar, M.A., 2010. On searching relevant studies in software engineering, in: *14th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE)*, pp. 1–10.
- Zhuang, T., Shi, J., 2024. Engagement, determinants and challenges: A multinational systematic review of education-focused university-industry collaborations. *Educational Review* 76, 1363–1391.